

NOTES

cooled and the solid obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The compounds gave single spots in tlc. IR : 3300-3400 cm^{-1} (ν CO.NH), 1220-1230 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C), 1160-1180 cm^{-1} (ν C=S) and 750-755 cm^{-1} (ν C-Cl).

3-(α -Aryloxyethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles^o(II): 1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (0.015 M) was refluxed in sodium hydroxide (35 ml, 8%) for 3 hrs, cooled and poured into large excess of water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a white solid which was washed and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The compounds thus obtained gave single spots in tlc. IR : 3250-3350 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1585-1600 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 1225-1230 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-) and 1160-1170 cm^{-1} (ν C=S).

2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles^o(III): 1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) was dissolved with cooling in conc. sulfuric acid (10 ml) and stirred well. The solution was left at room temperature for 2 hrs, and poured over crushed ice. It was diluted with water (50 ml) and filtered. The residue was washed with water, recrystallised from dilute alcohol and gave single spots on tlc. IR : 3250-3300 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1600-1615 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 1230-1250 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-) and 695-710 cm^{-1} (ν -S-).

2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles^o(IV): Mercuric oxide (0.011 M) was added to a methanolic solution of 1-(α -aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl-thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) and the whole refluxed for 1 to 3 hrs. The precipitated mercuric sulfide was filtered and washed on the filter with hot methanol. The filtrate on cooling gave a precipitate which was recrystallised from ethanol and gave a single spot on tlc. IR : 3280-3340 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1600-1630 cm^{-1} (ν C=N) and 1235-1260 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-).

Fungicidal screening: Fifteen compounds of Tables 1 and 2 were screened for their antifungal activity against *H. oryzae* and *A. brassicae* by agar plate technique¹⁰ at three different concentrations viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. All the compounds screened possessed moderate fungicidal activity against the above fungi.

The triazoles, though possessing higher antifungal activity than the parent thiosemicarbazides (I) and the corresponding oxadiazoles against *H. oryzae* display much less activity than the corresponding thiadiazoles. Against *A. brassicae*, the parent thiosemicarbazides are better fungicides than the corresponding triazoles which exhibit a little higher activity than the corresponding thiadiazoles and oxadiazole. Further the presence of chlorine atom ($R' = 4\text{-Cl}$) in the compounds increases the fungicidal activity over those having hydrogen or methyl group ($R' = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3$).

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Chemical and Pharmacological Studies on *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Seeds

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THE plant *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb. commonly known as *Rudraksha* in India belongs to the family *Elaeocarpaceae*¹. Chemical^{2,3} and pharmacological⁴⁻⁶ studies on this plant were reported earlier. The results of further chemical and pharmacological studies are presented in this paper.

Experimental

The crushed air-dried seeds of *E. ganitrus* (165 gms) were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 48 hrs and petroleum

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF OIL SEEDS AND OIL

Moisture%	8.87
Oil %	0.68
Colour of Oil	Pale Yellow
Consistency	Liquid
Refractive index at 30°	1.4650
Specific gravity at 32°	0.9300
Saponification value	176.0
Saponification equivalent	317.80
Iodine value	72.28
Acid value	34.89
Unsaponifiable Matter %	3.76

TABLE 2—RELATIVE PERCENTAGE COMPOSITION OF FATTY ACIDS IN TOTAL ACID PART OF THE OIL

Lauric Acid (12 : 0)	Myristic Acid (14 : 0)	Palmitic Acid (16 : 0)	Iso-palmitic Acid (16-iso)	Stearic Acid (18 : 0)	Iso-stearic Acid (18-iso)	Oleic Acid [18 : 1 (n-9)]	Linoleic Acid [18 : 2 (n-6)]
0.3	0.4	51.7	Trace	41.6	0.2	5.8	Trace

TABLE 3—RELATIVE PERCENTAGE COMPOSITION OF FATTY ACIDS IN EG-I

Myristic Acid (14 : 0)	Palmitic Acid (16 : 0)	Stearic Acid (18 : 0)	Oleic Acid [18 : 1 (n-9)]	Linoleic Acid [18 : 2 (n-6)]
1.78	61.78	14.18	19.73	2.73

ether was distilled off. A pale yellow oil (1.130 gms) was obtained. This was purified by filtering through animal charcoal and drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The characteristics of the oil were determined by conventional methods^{7,8,9} and the results are presented in Table 1.

The extracted oil was saponified by the conventional method^{7,9}, the unsaponifiable matter was removed by diethylether and the fatty acids were liberated with dilute hydrochloric acid. Extraction with ether and usual work up gave a mixture of fatty acids which was esterified with diazomethane¹⁰. The methyl esters were purified by preparative tlc and subjected to glc analysis.

The glc apparatus used was F and M model 700R of Hewlett and Packard, U.S.A., analytical dual column gas chromatograph with flame ionization detector, column 15% DEGS supported on 100-200 mesh Gas Chrom P and packed into a 6'X 1/8" stainless steel column, temperature 160°, carrier gas nitrogen 40 ml/min. The results are presented in Table 2.

The pale yellow oil obtained from petroleum ether extract of the seeds was steam distilled and the steam volatile part was further purified by preparative tlc (silica gel G, solvent system ; n-hexane : acetic acid = 99 : 1, v/v). This fraction (EG-I), so isolated, m.p. 43-47°, crystallised from aqueous MeOH, was found to be a mixture of several fatty acids as evident from tlc, uv and ir spectra. (EG-I) on treatment with ethereal diazomethane gave a mixture of fatty acid methyl esters, which was further purified by preparative tlc. It showed a single spot in tlc, having Rf-value almost identical with that of an authentic sample of methyl stearate. Both showed bright bluish fluorescence on tlc plate when viewed under uv light after spraying with 2',7'-dichloro fluorescein¹¹. (EG-I) was analysed by glc by the same procedure as mentioned earlier and the results are presented in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

Pharmacological actions¹² : In animal studies (EG-I) was found to possess dose-related pressor and myocardial stimulant properties. The pressor

effect was due partly to myocardial stimulation and partly to vasoconstriction. The vasoconstrictor effect was due to muscletropic action unrelated to alpha adrenoceptive receptors. The myocardial stimulation was more marked in hypodynamic hearts and atrial preparations. (EG-I) was, however, found to be devoid of any activity on the central nervous system. Earlier, Elliot *et al*¹³ and Chopde *et al*¹⁴ also reported that fatty acids possess a stimulating effect on the cardiac output, more marked in failing hearts. The details of the pharmacological tests will be published elsewhere.

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**Crystalline Components of the Stem
Heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* and
the Roots Heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata***

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RANDIA *dumatorium* (Rubiaceae) is a small tree and in the indigenous system of medicine is used as a substitute for ipecacuanha (*Cephaelis ipecacuanha*). It is nauseant expectorant and diaphoretic and is considered to have anthelmintic and abortifacient properties. The fruit is said to be useful as nervine calmative and antispasmodic¹⁻². Literature revealed that some work has been reported on its stem bark³⁻⁴ and fruits⁵.

Kigelia pinnata is a small spreading tree (Bignoniaceae) with a long-stalked large gourd like fruit. The fruit is used in Africa as dressing for ulcer and for syphilis, rheumatism and as a purgative. The bark is used in rheumatism, dysentery and venereal diseases⁶. Govindachari *et al* have reported the isolation of two new dihydroisocoumarins from its roots⁷⁻⁸. The present paper describes the chemical examination of the stem heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* and the roots heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata*.

Experimental

The stem of *Randia dumatorium* and the roots of *Kigelia pinnata* used in this investigation were collected in Jaipur. A voucher specimen from this collection has been deposited in the herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur.

Microanalysis was carried out by the Australian Microanalytical Service, Division of Applied Organic Chemistry, CSIRO and University of Melbourne. Thin layer chromatographs were conducted on Merck's Kiesel gel G; in chromatographic fractionations silica gel and neutral Brockmann alumina were used and the spray reagent used in tlc was 2% ceric sulphate in 2N H₂SO₄. All melting points are uncorrected. The identity of the compounds was confirmed, unless otherwise stated, by m.m.p. co-tlc and comparison of spectra with authentic samples.

Stem Heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* : Completely dried and coarsely powdered stem heartwood (4 kg) was extracted with benzene for 3×12 hrs on steam bath. The extract was concentrated under

reduced pressure to 200 ml. The dark red benzene extract was kept in the refrigerator overnight, when a solid mass separated at the bottom. This was removed by decantation and purified by washing with benzene, when colourless crystals, subsequently identified as mannitol, were obtained. The remaining portion of the extract was chromatographed over silica gel, when the following compounds were obtained : 1. α -Amyrin-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fraction, m.p. 183-84°, colourless shining needles, acetate, m.p. 222-23°; 2. β -Sitosterol-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3), fraction, colourless flakes m.p. 136-37°, acetate, m.p. 126-27°, benzoate, m.p. 143°; 3. *Oleanolic acid*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 304-5°, acetate, m.p. 266-67°; 4. *Ursolic acid*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, white needles, m.p. 284-85°, methyl ester, m.p. 168° and acetyl methyl ursolate, m.p. 242°; 5. *D-mannitol*-colourless crystals, m.p. 164-65°, identical with an authentic specimen, hexa-acetate m.p. 120°, phenylurethane, m.p. 301°, hexabenzate, m.p. 147-48°.

Roots Heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata* : The air dried roots (5 kg) were extracted with benzene for 12×3 hrs on water bath. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and was chromatographed over silica gel, when the following compounds were obtained : 1. *Octacosanol*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), m.p. 85°; acetate, m.p. 63-64°, iodide, m.p. 62-60°; 2. *Lapachol*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fraction, fine yellow needles, m.p. 139-40°; 3. β -*Sitosterol*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) fraction, colourless flakes, m.p. 136-37°, acetate, m.p. 126-27°, benzoate, m.p. 143°; 4. *Kigelin*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 144°; 5. *Stigmasterol*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 170°, acetate, m.p. 144°, benzoate, m.p. 160°; 6. *Rhodamine B*-from ethyl acetate-methanol (3 : 1) fraction, gave bright pink spot on tlc plate. On crystallization, furnished dark green crystals M⁺ C₂₈H₂₉N₂O₃. UV(MeOH) λ_{max} 260, 310, 360, 550 nm, finally confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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